

An efficient procedure for preconcentration of cadmium using modified sawdust as an adsorbent

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Abstract : A procedure for the separation and preconcentration of trace amounts of cadmium is proposed. It is based on the adsorption of CdCl_3^- ions solution onto a column of sawdust modified with diethylenetriamine. Cadmium complex is quantitatively retained on the column in the pH range 3–5.5. The cadmium complex was eluted with 2 mL of nitric acid and cadmium was measured by flame atomic absorption spectrometry. Ten replicate determinations of 5 and 25 ng mL^{-1} of cadmium gave a relative standard deviation of 2.42 and 1.19%, respectively. The limit of detection based on $3S_b$, was 0.20 ng mL^{-1} . The interference of large number of anions and cations was studied. The procedure was applied to the determination of cadmium in several natural water samples. The standard addition technique was applied and the obtained recoveries revealed that the proposed procedure has a good accuracy. A high preconcentration factor (250), simplicity and high regeneration of adsorbent were the main advantages in this analytical method.

Keywords : Cadmium, preconcentration, modified sawdust, adsorption, diethylenetriamine.

Introduction

In recent years, pollution by heavy metals including cadmium has received considerable attention. Cadmium has been described as one of the most dangerous trace elements in the environment¹. This element accumulates in living organisms and has a high toxic potential. Now-a-days, many separation/preconcentration techniques for metal ions determination include liquid-liquid extraction², cloud point extraction³, dispersive liquid-liquid micro-extraction⁴ and solid-phase extraction⁵. Of all these methods, solid phase extraction has been widely used in comparison with traditional extraction techniques; since it is simple, rapid, inexpensive, less polluting to the environment and can be easily automated¹. The choice of appropriate sorbent for solid phase extraction is a critical parameter in order to obtain full recovery and high enrichment factor⁶. For this reason introducing new sorbent is still a challenge for analytical chemists⁵. Various sorption materials, such as modified activated carbon⁷, modified naphthalene⁸, carbon nanotube⁹, modified silica membrane¹⁰, modified silica gel¹¹, modified nano-alumina¹², wool-packed microcolumn¹³ and modified

ambersorb 572¹⁴ have been used for preconcentration of cadmium that each one has advantages and disadvantages.

In this study, modified sawdust by diethylenetriamine (DETA) is used as adsorbent. Cadmium as CdCl_3^- is preconcentrated by adsorption on modified sawdust, eluted by nitric acid and determined by FAAS.

Experimental

Apparatus and materials :

In this research, the following apparatus were employed : A flame atomic absorption spectrometer, manufactured by PG Instrument, model PG990 : Carry 100; a pH meter, manufactured by Horiba, model : F11.

All reagents were analytical grade and were used without further purification. A 1000 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ stock solution of cadmium(II) was prepared by dissolving 0.2745 g of cadmium(II) nitrate tetrahydrate (Merck) in 100 mL. Working solutions were freshly prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution with water. A solution of potassium chloride (KCl) 4.0 mol L^{-1} was prepared by dissolving 29.82 g of KCl (Merck) in water and diluting to

100 mL in a volumetric flask. The pH adjustments were made with 0.01 mol L⁻¹ of HCl or NaOH. A buffer solution of pH 4.0 was prepared by adding 0.2 mol L⁻¹ of NaOH to 0.2 mol L⁻¹ acid formic and using a pH meter to adjust the pH.

Preparation of adsorbent :

The sawdust supplied by a local wood processing factory was washed with distilled water to remove impurity, and then was dried overnight at 60 °C. The dried sawdust was sieved to retain the 0.5 mm fractions for further chemical synthesis. 140 mL of HCl concentrated (Merck) was added to 10 g of sawdust. After 2 h, 60 mL of diethylenetriamine (Merck) was added too. Then, the product was filtered, washed with distilled water, and dried in oven at 40 °C for 24 h.

General procedure :

A glass tube (70 mm length and 6 mm i.d) with a very fine bore was used as a preconcentration column. It was filled with the adsorbent (0.3 g) then slightly pressing the adsorbent in the column with a flat glass rod. 500 mL solutions containing 1–50 ng mL⁻¹ of cadmium, 15 mL of potassium chloride (4 mol L⁻¹) to give a final concentration of 0.06 mol L⁻¹ KCl, 2 mL of formate buffer solution (pH 4) was passed through the column. The column packing was then washed with a small volume of water. The metal complex was eluted with 2 mL of 0.5 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid.

The eluents were collected in a 2 mL volumetric flask, made up to the mark with water. Then, cadmium was determined by FAAS. The recovery of the metal ions was calculated from the ratio of the concentration found by FAAS to what calculated theoretically.

Results and discussion

DETA-sawdust was chosen as an adsorbent for solid phase extraction of Cd^{II}. DETA-sawdust has many amino groups¹⁵. The preliminary experimental observations showed that its chloride complex (CdCl₃⁻) is adsorbed on DETA-sawdust by forming an ion pair in acidic condition. The adsorbed metal complex is eluted by nitric acid solution from the column of DETA-sawdust (recovery >

90%), while the sawdust did not have this ability (recovery < 40%).

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the preconcentration of 0.5 µg mL⁻¹ of cadmium was studied in the range of about 2.5–7.5 by the addition of HCl or NaOH and applying the general procedure. Fig. 1 shows the influence of pH on the recovery of the cadmium. As it is observed maximum recovery is obtained in the range of 3.5–5.0. Therefore, pH 4 was chosen for further work. Different buffer systems, with pH 4 such as acetate and formate, were examined and formate buffer was selected because it did not change the recovery of the solution after preconcentration. Thus, 2 mL of formate buffer pH 4 was added to the sample solutions to maintain the pH at 4.

Fig. 1. The effect of pH on the recovery of Cd.

(Concentration of Cd = 500 ng mL⁻¹, volume of the sample = 50 mL, chloride concentration = 0.2 mol L⁻¹).

Effect of chloride concentration :

The effect of the chloride concentration on the recovery was studied by passing 50 mL of a solution containing 0.5 µg mL⁻¹ of Cd and 2 mL of formate buffer through the column. The chloride concentration was varied in the range of 0.00 to 0.20 mol L⁻¹ and the recovery was determined by FAAS after preconcentration following the general procedure. The results are shown in Fig. 2. It was found that the recovery of Cd increased up to a chloride concentration of 0.10 mol L⁻¹ and reached a plateau above that. Therefore, a chloride concentration of 0.12 mol L⁻¹ in the final solution was selected for the further experiments.

Fig. 2. The effect of chloride concentration on the recovery of Cd. (Concentration of Cd = 500 ng mL⁻¹, volume of the sample = 50 mL, pH = 4).

Choice of eluent :

A satisfactory eluent should quantitatively elute the sorbed analytes with small volume, which is needed for a high enrichment factor. For this reason, various solutions such as nitric acid, hydrochloric acid, thiourea 5% and thioacetamide 5% were used to identify the best eluent for the sorbed metal on the DETA-sawdust sorbent. Among the eluents, nitric acid provided higher recoveries compared to thiourea 5%, thioacetamide 5% and hydrochloric acid. Therefore, the effect of nitric acid concentration was studied. The results indicated that the highest recoveries were obtained when nitric acid concentration was above 0.2 M. Thus, 0.5 M of nitric acid was chosen as the eluent. The effect of volume of nitric acid was also investigated and quantitative recoveries were obtained for 2–5 mL of the eluent. The optimum eluent volume was specified as 2 mL for the subsequent studies.

The effect of the mass of adsorbent :

In order to test the effect of the mass of adsorbent on quantitative retention of CdCl₃⁻ complex, different amounts of DETA-sawdust adsorbent (0.05–0.60 g) were chosen and the experimental method was applied. Quantitative adsorption was not obtained when the mass of adsorbent was smaller than 0.2 g. Thus, 0.3 g of DETA-sawdust was selected for further studies.

Effect of sample volume :

For the preconcentration of trace elements, it is desirable to consider a variety of preconcentration factors. In order to achieve a high preconcentration factor, the breakthrough volume of sample solution should be established. The effect of sample volume on the adsorption of CdCl₃⁻ complex was studied in the range of 50–500 mL. Each solution contained, same amount of Cd²⁺ and the adsorption and desorption processes were performed under the optimum conditions. The results showed that the CdCl₃⁻ present in various volumes of solution was completely and quantitatively adsorbed on DETA-sawdust. The adsorption decreased at higher volumes than 500 mL. Therefore, determine trace quantities of Cd²⁺ in samples, a sample volume up to 500 mL could be selected in order to increase the preconcentration factor to 250.

Regeneration columnn :

Regeneration studies of the adsorbent are of great importance because these are helpful to explore the possibility of recycling the adsorbents and the recovery of sorbed materials from the adsorbent. In this research, for regeneration study, a glass tube (70 mm length and 6 mm i.d) with a very fine bore was used as a regeneration column. It was filled with 0.3 g adsorbent after slightly pressing the adsorbent in the column with a flat glass rod. 500 mL solutions containing 20 ng/mL of cadmium (in optimum condition) was passed through the column. The column was eluted with 2 mL of 0.5 mol/L HNO₃. Then, the column was washed with 300 mL of water. This cycle was repeated 5 times, in all cycles the recovery was about 100%. These results show that the adsorbent has a high capability for regeneration.

Analytical performance :

A linear calibration graph was drawn for the determination of cadmium under the proposed experimental conditions. The data yielded a good linearity in the range of 1–50 ng mL⁻¹ cadmium. The equation of the line was $A = 0.0173C + 0.0548$ with a regression coefficient of $r = 0.9953$ ($n = 10$). The limit of detection (LOD),

defined as the concentration of the analyte giving signals equivalent to three standard deviations of the blank ($3S_b$), was 0.20 ng mL^{-1} and the relative standard deviations (RSD) for ten replicate measurements of 5 and 25 ng mL^{-1} of cadmium was 2.42 and 1.19%, respectively.

Interference studies :

In order to evaluate the selectivity of the method, the effects of different ions on the solid phase extraction and determination of cadmium were investigated. A constant concentration of cadmium (20 ng mL^{-1}) was taken with different concentrations of ions and the general procedure was followed. Any deviation of $\pm 5\%$ or more from the absorbance value of the standard solution was considered as interference. Results given in Table 1 indicate

The interference of Cu^{II} was eliminated by using thio-sulfate sodium as a masking agent. Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} were masked with sodium fluoride.

Application :

The proposed preconcentration procedure was applied to the determination of trace cadmium in water samples. Different amounts of cadmium were spiked to the tap, river, mineral and wastewater samples and the resulting solutions were submitted to the preconcentration procedure. The results are given in Table 2. A good agreement was obtained between the added and found analyte content using the recommended procedure. The recovery value for the analyte ions was in the range of 91–95.5%. As can be seen, the proposed method gave good recoveries.

Table 1. Comparison of present method with previously reported

Adsorbent	PF	RSD (%)	LOD (ng/mL)	AM (g)	Ref.
Modified active carbon	290	1.4	2.1	0.6	7
Modified naphthalene	40	1.05	0.6	–	8
Carbone nanotube	40	1.42	0.43	0.15	9
Modified silica membrane	200	≤ 2.0	5.0	–	10
Modified silica gel	30	1.1	0.5	–	11
Modified nano-alumina	250	2.8	0.15	–	12
Wool-packed microcolumn	39	3.4	0.037	–	13
Modified Ambersorb 572	200	1.9	0.032	–	14
Modified sawdust	250	1.19	0.201	0.3	This work

PF : Preconcentration factor, AM : Adsorbent mass.

that the proposed method is relatively selective for the determination of cadmium.

Table 2. Effect of the interference of diverse ions on the recovery of cadmium

Diverse ion	Tolerance ratio (Foreign species conc./ Cd^{2+} conc.)
Na^+ , CH_3COO^- , HPO_4^- , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$, Ba^{2+} , CrO_4^-	1000
Pb^{2+} , Ag^+ , CO_3^{2-} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Hg^{2+}	400
Sn^{2+}	200
Fe^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , S^{2-}	100

Table 3. Determination of cadmium in real samples

Sample	Cd (ng mL ⁻¹)		Recovery (%)
	Added	Found ^a	
Tap water	0	4.5 ± 0.1	–
	10	50.0 ± 0.6	91.02
	30	96.4 ± 0.9	95.29
Mineral water	0	0.7 ± 0.05	–
	10	47.9 ± 0.5	94.70
	30	98.8 ± 0.8	94.31
River water	0	4.1 ± 0.1	–
	10	51.2 ± 0.6	93.91
	30	98.9 ± 0.9	95.53
Waste water	0	4.3 ± 0.08	–
	10	52.6 ± 0.7	92.50
	30	102.0 ± 0.9	95.04

Conclusions

The proposed method is simple, rapid, reproducible and sensitive and can be applied for the determination of cadmium. Sawdust modified with DETA. The prepared sorbent is economical and the method is highly selective for the determination of trace amounts of cadmium by flame atomic absorption spectrometry. In the case of working with large sample volume solutions of about 500 mL and also small extracting solvent volume of 2.0 mL, 250 fold preconcentration factor is achieved. The method compares favorably with most of the published methods for the determination of cadmium using flame atomic absorption (Table 3)⁷⁻¹⁴. The limit of detection⁷⁻¹¹ and preconcentration factor^{8-11,13,14} of the proposed method is better than many methods. The analytical parameters together with the values obtained in the analyzed samples show the usefulness of the method for measuring Cd^{II} tap, river, mineral and wastewater samples.

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